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ROADMAP TOWARDS ORGANIZATIONAL GOAL OF BULACAN AGRICULTURAL STATE COLLEGE, PHILIPPINES: NARRATOLOGY ON ADMINISTRATIVE THOUGHT OF AN INSTITUTION LEADER

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Abstract:

The day-to-day activities of a higher education institution usually involve the implementation of its institutional mandate. The achievement of the organizational objective in the direction of its Roadmap is also a common priority. It is misleading that the administration lies only on the shoulder of the President of the State College as the chief manager and head of the institution. The administration also takes place in the institution, however, as soon as the staff enters the institution. Institutional administration by the President of the State College is also based on guiding principles and philosophical administrative thought. This philosophy will be explored in this paper and will be interpreted through a well-managed higher education institution. This paper will provide an explanation of the philosophical administrative thought of the President of Bulacan Agricultural State College in the field of institutional administration. This paper will also generate a philosophic/theoretical model that will describe the current philosophy as the president, being in the top management of the organization, practicing leadership and management at the state college.

Key Words:

Philosophy, Administrative Thought, Higher Education.

1. Introduction

Some excellent anthologies on administrative thinking have been published in recent years. They present essays, research and book selections on a variety of subjects that are essentially considered to be general in the understanding of educational philosophy. There are several theories and practices involved in management. Top-level education management can be anchored in the bureaucratic theory of Max Weber. Max Weber (1864–1920) described the theory of an organization known as the Bureaucratic Management Approach or the Weber Bureaucracy. Weber's theory explicitly describes the structure of hierarchical management. This structure also describes the organizational structure of a higher education institution. In addition, the bureaucratic theory defines the characteristics of each employee in an organization to be qualified for a particular expertise. This concept is evident in the maximization of the division of labor in the workplace. The higher education institution consists of several institutes and sub-offices which are assigned to a specific task in order to be effective. In addition, the selection of employees who lead to their promotion is based on the experience, competence and technical qualifications demonstrated by examinations, education or training.

Over the years, research studies have focused on management. According to Northouse (2010), management is a universally appealing subject that has posed a major challenge to practitioners and researchers interested in understanding the nature of leadership. It continues to be a “highly valued phenomenon that is very complex” (p. 12).

The objectives of this paper are to outline the institutional roadmap of the institution; to determine the administrative thought and skills of the president of the institution; to determine the role of philosophy in the administration of the institution; and to generate a philosophical model that exposes the significant contribution of administrative thought to education.

State college and university presidents are concerned with the management of an executive position. It is indeed a great challenge for the President of the State College to deal with conflicts and challenges within their jurisdiction. In southern Illinois, for example, the president of the university faced serious challenges in addressing students and families with problems that threaten the school community, as they often move from place to place, apparently under the driving force of poverty. School teachers must, however, allow potentially dangerous students labeled homeless to be registered (Baker & Prusaczyk, 2011). Not to exaggerate, but today, education leaders have such an enormous task to address the many aspects that communities bring to the university. For example, Millerborg (1990)

sought to determine whether administrators are able to make ethical and legal decisions and to identify differences between them in the decisions of educational administrators, in particular where ethics is in conflict with the law.

Hudgens (1991) concluded that 50 percent or more of the university and college presidents saw an increased workload, a harmful effect on district funding, and no significant progress at the local or state level. The findings have clearly shown some of the important issues that affect the decision of teachers. These are reflected in the issues of most college-related studies and somewhat reflect current problems (e.g. Dexheimer, 1970; Fenstermaker, 1994). In addition, all aspects of the organization are covered by the multi-functional task of the college president as school leader and manager. Some of these aspects include intensified circumstances. During the school community recovery process, maintaining this focus and awareness of security during and after a tragic event is a challenge for college professors (Williams, 2014). Administration is a key component of change and strategic innovation in which leaders work through difficult situations (Smith & Riley, 2012). Teachers and school administrators face crisis situations. Emergency situations exist without warning, and teachers and administrators need to be prepared. How school leaders deal with the crisis and the process of recovery will determine the progress of the school community (Williams, 2014).

Institution leaders may have many different situations to deal with. Kowalski, McCord, Petersen, Young, and Ellerson (2011) agree that “to fully appreciate the complexity of this pivotal position and its evolution over more than 100 years, it must be understood how duties and responsibilities have increased and decreased over time” (p. 1). The importance of top-level education management studies suggests that college presidents who serve as educational leaders are a significant factor in the overall achievement of their institutions (Bjork, 2009). Evidence that the challenges of institution leaders are abundant (Antonucci, 2012).

Top-level management in a higher education institution lies on the shoulder of the State College President. The President of the College exercises all aspects of management control within his / her jurisdiction. The Higher Education Institution is leading the roadmap towards success. The President of the State College, as the leader of the institution, provides an immediate and responsive solution to any challenge faced by the College. The President of the State College faces issues and challenges that he / she may face along the way. Whatever the course of action taken by the president of the state college, he / she is ready to face the consequences.

These situations are some of the administrative issues where philosophy needs to be observed. From seeking possible answers to emerging challenges and issues, to innovating relevant interventions to improve institutional governance.

1.1. The Institutional Background

The main campus of Bulacan Agricultural State College (BASC) is currently located in Barangay Pinaod, San Ildefonso district, Bulacan. Before it became BASC, it was established in 1952 as the Plaridel Community Agricultural High School (PCAHS) located in Brgy. Bintog, Plaridel, Bulacan (Senate of the Philippines, 1952). The name PCAHS soon changed to Bulacan Provincial Agricultural High School (BPAHS). The number of students started from 100 and increased over time. BPAHS has also begun to accommodate students not only from local communities but also from other neighboring municipalities. The Republic Act 948 of June 20, 1953 turned BPAHS' name from Provincial to National having the name Bulacan National Agricultural High School (BNAHS) due to nationalization of existing agricultural schools (The Corpus Juris, 2020).

By Proclamation No. 163 of former President Ramon DF. Magsaysay, 8 June 1955, 192.5 hectares of the Buenavista Estate reserved for BNAHS (Official Gazette, 1955). After four years of operation as BNAHS, its name was changed to Bulacan National Agricultural School (BuNAS) by virtue of the Republic Act 2416 of 21 June 1959. In 1960, the two-year program Associate in Agriculture became part of the curriculum of BuNAS; the first higher education program offered at the school, which eventually led to the offering of a Bachelor of Science in Agriculture with majors in Animal Husbandry and Agronomy.

Awareness at that time of the prevalent agricultural education and training needs of the Bulacan people, Hon. Ricardo C. Silverio, then the 3rd District Representative of Bulacan, drafted House Bill No. 2389, which introduced an extended BuNAS education program. 1998 when it became a chartered college and changed its name to Bulacan National Agricultural State College (BNASC) by virtue of the Republic Act 8548. Later in 2004, from BNASC to its current BASC name.

Located between the country's capital, Metro Manila, and the Province of Nueva Ecija, it opened its doors in 1952 and 60 years later, BASC continues to devote itself to exploring solutions to this generation's profound problems and preparing students for leadership in today's multifaceted environment. In turn, BASC has become a national higher education pioneer and remains to be remembered for providing outstanding agricultural education, interdisciplinary collaborations and groundbreaking research programs in Bulacan.

However, the college also needs professional partners from different backgrounds to work with the administration in the form of realistic objectives. In order to realize this, BASC promotes partnership and modernization through traditional education boundaries, creating exceptional individuals who pass their mark on the planet. Above all, BASC continues to deliver on its commitment to graduates, successful research and education.

Like any well-respected educational institution, BASC has thought and worked on the wider world in the same way. Early on, the foundation was powerful and imaginative. For this great educational effort, teachers, students and alumni, sponsors and donors and supporters, through the leadership and management of the State College Administrator, have joined forces to meet the organizational objectives. Without their dreams, support and dedication, the BASC will never be the BASC of today.

The educational mission is now to help students learn about teamwork and problem-solving skills and values of excellence, moral behavior, a duty to society and a commitment to their potential jobs. Every effort is needed to train students for a sensible global citizenship and leadership by combining sustainability, public accountability and respect for diverse perspectives in their education, while at the same time gaining strong professional skills.

Since its inception, the BASC foundation has become a manifestation of the school management and administrative thought of every leader who led the school as a state college in Bulacan. It is interesting to note the contribution of the institutional leaders to the achievement of the organizational objective as they envision its road map towards success.

1.2. Management Significance

Understanding the administrative experience of the president of a state college in a higher education institution in Bulacan is not a common point of research interest in the field of education management. This paper presents the ideas and insights of an educational leader on top-level management to overcome organizational objectives to achieve personalized and customized leadership when administrative thought interferes. This study gives a definition of emerging administrative thought in the leadership and management of higher education institutions through narratology. Narrative research has a strong sketch in describing the personal experience of a state college president in running a higher education institution. This idea will give top-level managers and administrators significant and personal issues and concerns about taking responsibility for higher-level management.

2. Method

Two types of methods have been used in this academic paper. The first method was document research, followed by an interview with the President of the State College himself. Document research was primarily included as one of the methods used to understand the demographic profile and history of the school. The documents retrieved have played a vital role in establishing the demographic background of the location and subject of this paper. Interview with the President of the State College as an informant was quite significant since he was the primary agent in the administration and management of the institution. The President of the State College was given a set of interview guide questions that he answered. Along with the interview guide questions, follow-ups were provided to confirm and clarify some of the details of the information.

An off-cam interview was also planned to raise the tone of the interview process and reveal significant data on administrative thought at the Bulacan Agricultural State College. It is noteworthy because there were different insights and ideas raised during the session. The following results were discussed in the next part of this paper from the above methods of data collection.

3. Results and Discussion

The primary results of this concept paper were derived from the following results and discussions. The management and leadership style of the President of the State College demonstrates the challenges that arise along the way. Administrative thought, however, arbitrates on the basis of the President's desire as the overall leader.

3.1. Institutional Roadmap of BASC

Bulacan Agricultural State College's vision and mission is to be an outstanding institution of higher education in the country with excellent education and high-quality service. The institution's direction towards excellence is guided by the desired atmosphere of the president of higher education. In the case of BASC, however, the priorities for achieving its goal depend on the perception of the President of the State College.

The phases and objectives of the institution are modified and modified by the school administrator. The actions of the organizational leaders, in combination with the implementation of operational interventions, are essential for both the implementation and intervention outcomes (Lundmark, 2018). Results also suggest that intervention-specific behaviors of school administrators are directly related to implementation and intervention outcomes and should therefore be focused primarily on the assessment of organizational

intervention processes. This means that any organizational objective could be interfered with by the behavior of the school administrator through their administrative thought.

3.2. Administrative Skills of the State College President

The President of the Bulacan Agricultural State College shall serve the highest administration and supervision on a regular basis. The President of the State College was able to manage institutional activities and address issues and challenges at his executive level.

Policy implementation has been consistently monitored across the institute. In addition, the task assigned to all instructors and professors, including staff, has been carried out on a regular basis. Commonalities can be found among the management practices of the President of the State College. Its refined structure has been used to document patterns based on Planning, Organizing, Staffing, Directing, Coordinating, Reporting and Budgeting (POSDCoRB) in parts as well as in whole. While the elements of POSDCoRB are certainly not the only patterns of administration, they may represent the core (Chalekian, 2013). In the same way, the president of the state college carries out the manifestations of the 14 principles of governance.

Giving directions lies in the hands of the president of the state college. After giving the right task to the right person, the president of the state college gives direction on how his / her people perform the assigned task. Leadership is the skill of leaders and managers through the establishment of the team's efforts to achieve organizational goals and objectives (McGregor, 1957).

Based on the informant's response, it is the skills of the President of the State College to connect different units and sections and to achieve absolute cooperation within the organization. The president of the state college placed himself in a higher perspective to see the overview of what is going on in the campus and in the institutes. From this perspective, the President of the State College is in a position to coordinate assignments and tasks with the staff of the institutes. Coordination may also lead to the synchronization of work towards the achievement of the organizational objective.

3.3. The Role of the President in Administration

The hard part of being the President of the State College is the breadth and intensity of roles and responsibilities. In the wider arena, the President of the State College faces a number of challenges and obstructions to organizational excellence. As President of the State College, all responsibilities should be fulfilled. As preventive intervention, leadership and management

are delegated to the Institute's deans, directors and vice-presidents. The transfer of instructions takes place when the President of the State College needs to broaden the reach of his or her hands to address problems and challenges and to carry out large-scale responsibilities.

Indeed, the responsibilities of a top-level position include the vertical and lateral directions of organizational management and leadership. In the top management, both challenging and exciting are expected. This section exposed the extraordinary role of the President of the State College in managing a higher education institution, regardless of the variety and never-ending encounters within and outside the organization, in order to achieve excellence and exemplary performance.

Part of the task of managing the performance of the President of the State College is to ensure that the performance of each individual and institute is objective. Performance management creates a positive relationship between employees (Zhang, 2012; Dewydar, 2015). Evaluation is always carried out through evidence-based means of verification. For those who have not achieved a commendable performance, the office of the President of the State College has always provided technical assistance and support. This technical assistance is driving the people of the organization towards a progressive routine.

3.4. Emerging Administrative Thought

The emerging administrative thought in this chapter is positive collaboration and a strong relationship between people within the organization. Working together with the team will lead to any effort being made. The President of the State College embraces the potential of each and every member of the institute and unit by providing technical and moral support to the faculty and staff of the institution. The good relationship shown by the President of the State College for the past year of his administration is a good indication and manifestation of organizational success and excellence.

A positive collaboration and a strong relationship between the President of the State College and the faculty and staff have resulted in a progressive impact on sustainable organizational success. The implications of the joint effort between the leader and the members of the organization are clearly discussed. The hand-in-hand working relationship between the President of the State College and the faculty and staff should therefore be maintained and preserved.

The schematic diagram shown in Figure 1 describes the philosophical model of administrative thought applied to school management education. This idea suggested that the administrative

thought of the top managers could interfere with any institutional roadmap and direction. As a result of the data provided by the President of the State College, the administrative thought focuses on projecting, planning, peopling and programing (4Ps). As derived from the narrative of the President of the State College, these 4Ps are the primary considerations of administrative thought.

Projecting is the initial factor of the administrative thought where the President of the State College, as the leader of the institution, predicts the vision of the organization. It is the stage before planning. At this point, the leader of the institution projects the potential activities as well as the resources that might be needed. Planning will take place after the planning phase. Institution leaders plan to manage and control all resources very well. Planning also minimizes the risk of not meeting the target. The next focus of the administrative thought is on people. It involves the provision of human resources and staffing. This administrative thought focuses on the idea of putting the right person on the right task to ensure that the expected time and output will be achieved. Finally, programing focuses on setting and adjusting the implementation in order to achieve controllable organizational objectives.

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of the Philosophical Model of Administrative Thought Applied to Education

4. Conclusion and Recommendations

The achievement of any organizational objective is always identified through institutional roadmaps and objectives. However, the direction of the roadmap is being taken by the administrative thought of the President of the State College. It is at the command of the

president of the state college that they want to justify the organization's objective. In addition, the administrative thought of the President of the State College, as the leader of the institution, focuses on projecting, planning, peopling and programing.

The search for answers to some relevant, or sometimes irrelevant, questions in dealing with management issues and challenges is often ignored or misled by instructors, professors, teachers and administrators. Based on the findings of the study, look for the true reason/s of what is happening at a higher education institution in times of administrative dilemma. It is highly recommended that all faculty and staff work together on the administrative thought set out by the president of the college / university. Productive consultative conferences may help to highlight all issues and concerns related to policy implementation and evaluation. Through these activities, the faculty and staff, as well as the President of the College, will have a clearer perspective on the real picture of the institution from an individual point of view—from the experience of the teachers and compare it with that of the President of the College. This may also lead to the smooth running of the school and its management.

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